

A review of the Evolution of Text Vectorisation Techniques - From Bag-Of-Words to Contextualised Embeddings.

1st Cian Smith

Atlantic Technological University

Department of Computer Science & Applied Physics

Galway, Ireland

g00472754@atu.ie

Abstract—This paper presents a comprehensive review of the evolution of text vectorisation techniques in Natural Language Processing (NLP), text classification, and Information Retrieval (IR), tracing the progression from early methods like Bag-of-Words (BoW) and Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) to advanced contextual embeddings derived from models such as Embeddings from Language Models (ELMo) and Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT). It examines the strengths and limitations of each approach, highlighting how recent innovations—particularly those involving large language models (LLMs)—have addressed previous shortcomings, and suggests future research into the performance of attention mechanisms and their alternatives.

Index Terms—Text Vectorisation, Bag-of-Words, Tf-Idf, Embeddings, Word2Vec, Doc2Vec, Transformers, ELMo, BERT

I. INTRODUCTION

Text vectorisation is a fundamental process in Natural Language Processing (NLP), transforming textual data into numerical representations that machine learning models can interpret. Over the decades, vectorisation techniques have evolved significantly—from simple frequency-based models like Bag-of-Words (BoW) and Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) to sophisticated neural embeddings that capture semantic and contextual nuances. This evolution reflects the growing complexity and demands of NLP tasks, necessitating more nuanced representations of language. This paper delves into the progression of text vectorisation methods, examining how each advancement has addressed the limitations of its predecessors and exploring recent trends that promise to further enhance the efficacy of text representations in machine learning applications.

Fig. 1. Timeline of Technique Evolution

II. RELATED WORKS

Choice of vectorisation technique is an important part of NLP. As such, there have been numerous studies to investigate and compare the performance of various techniques for NLP applications such as Text Classification.

Abubakar et al. investigated the performance of Bag of Words, TF-IDF, Word2Vec, and Doc2Vec vectorisation for sentiment classification [1]. The research showed that, despite being developed decades before Word2Vec and Doc2Vec, TF-IDF was the best performer for sentiment classification. However, it also suggested that a combination of TF-IDF and Word2Vec can perform even better.

Vectorisation for Text Classification with a focus on memory usage was explored by Rani et al. in 2022 [2]. The comparison between various vectorisation techniques including TF-IDF, Word2Vec, GloVe, and Doc2Vec concluded that Doc2Vec used the least memory post vectorisation and led to reductions in both training and testing times for classification models.

Krzyszewska et al. [3] explored the performance of different vectorisation methods for classification. In their work, they highlighted the effectiveness and efficiency of various text vectorisation techniques (with Doc2Vec being the most recent method) when working with large datasets. It was found that the performance of word-based vectorisation and whole text vectorisation had similar classification results.

While previous reviews have discussed how vectorisation techniques perform for specific tasks, I would like to explore how the problems of previous techniques were solved as new techniques have evolved, and see how the limitations of modern techniques may be addressed by current or future research.

III. EVOLUTION

A. Early beginnings

1) **Bag-of-Words**: First proposed by linguist Zellig S. Harris in his 1954 article “Distributional Structure” [4], Bag-of-Words (BoW) is recognised as the first form of text vectorisation. This technique builds a vocabulary consisting of each word that appears in a corpus (the collection of all

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF TEXT VECTORISATION TECHNIQUES

Technique	Era	Dimensionality	Context	Model Type	Strengths	Weaknesses
Bag-of-Words	Pre-2010	High	✗ No	Statistical	Simple, fast	Sparse, ignores word order
TF-IDF	Pre-2010	High	✗ No	Statistical	Highlights important words	Still sparse, no semantics
Word2Vec	2013	Medium	✗ No	Neural (shallow)	Semantic similarity	No polysemy support
FastText	2016	Medium	✗ No	Neural (subword)	Handles OOV words, morphology-aware	Static context, less nuanced semantics
ELMo	2018	Medium	✓ Yes (biLM)	Contextual	Dynamic embeddings	Large, sequential, slow
BERT	2018	High	✓ Yes	Transformer-based	Deep context, bidirectional	Computationally intensive

text/documents to be used for training and/or evaluation). Each vocabulary entry for a document is then given a number corresponding with the frequency it appears (alternatively, a binary value indicating the presence of a word in the text). Therefore, the dimensionality of each vector is the size of the vocabulary. The result is a sparse vector that fails to capture the relationship between words, context, or the meaning of words. Despite its age, BoW is a technique that is still used today, and is the foundation for other vectorisation methods.

And example of BoW can be seen in the related works by Abubakar et al. [1] using these sentences: Sent 1: “Shah is a good writer” Sent 2: “To be a good writer, you need to practice” Sent 3: “I enjoyed every bit of it”

The resulting vectors from these sentences can be seen in Table II.

TABLE II
BAG OF WORDS REPRESENTATION OF WORDS (ABUBAKAR, 2020) [1]

	Shah	Is	a	good	writer	To	Be	you	Need	Practice	Enjoyed	every	bit	of	it
Sent 1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sent 2	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sent 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1

2) **Bag-of-N-grams**: Bag-of-n-grams (BoN) extends BoW to word sequences. A n-gram refers to a sequence of ‘n’ words (or characters). The concept of n-grams was first proposed by Claude E. Shannon in his 1948 paper “A Mathematical Theory of Communication” [5] as a method of modeling language entropy and predictability. Instead of creating a vocabulary of words, a vocabulary of word sequences (alternatively, character sequences) of size ‘n’ is built. BON has the advantage of capturing phrases and limited context, however, the trade off is a much larger dimensionality, as unique word sequences are much more numerous than individual words.

In computing, the practical implementation of BoW can be referred to as Count Vectorisation.

3) **TF - IDF**: Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), when combined with BpW, allows the importance of a word to a document to be represented in the vector. TF simply refers to the frequency a term (e.g. word) appears in a document.

$$TF(t, d) = \frac{\text{Number of times term } t \text{ appears in document } d}{\text{Total number of terms in document } d}$$

The concept of IDF was first presented by Karen Spärck Jones in 1972 [6]. The basic principle is that the more a term

appears across the corpus, the less importance it has.

$$IDF(t) = \log \left(\frac{\text{Total number of documents}}{\text{Number of documents containing term } t} \right)$$

TF and IDF were combined by Salton et al. in their 1987 paper ‘Term Weighting Approaches in Automatic Text Retrieval’ [7].

$$TF\text{-}IDF(t, d) = TF(t, d) \times IDF(t)$$

As previously stated, with BoW, replacing simple word frequency counts with TF-IDF means the resulting vector includes information on the importance a word has to the document. Frequently occurring words (e.g. the, of, and) will therefore be given small values in the vector.

This, of course, does not solve BoW’s issue with sparsity, and while a word’s importance to a document is captured, its relationship to the words around it is still not represented in the vector, nor the meaning of the word.

B. Distributed Representations

1) **Word2Vec**: Up until this point, vectorisation of text mainly focused on creating a single vector for a document. In 2013 there was shift towards word vectors. Mikolov et al. [8] proposed two new architectures to vectorise text: Continuous Bag-of-Words (CBoW) and Continuous Skip-grams. CBoW was designed to predict a word based on the words surround it, while the Skip-gram model predicts the surrounding context when given a single word. This resulted in a number of improvements to text vectorisation:

- A Vectors are now dense. Previously, with BoW representations, if a vocabulary word was not in the text it was represented by a 0. Now, each word in the text is represented by 50, 100, or even 300+ numbers (the dimension of the vector), none of which are 0.
- B The meaning of a word is captured. The vector representation of a word is determined by its context (surrounding words), this mean words with similar meanings (e.g. synonyms) would have similar vectors.
- C Vectors are no longer hand crafted. Previously, vectors depended on the corpus it was going to be used for. Now, word vectors are independent of corpus, as they are learned representations.

These vectors are essentially the weights of a neural network trained on a large corpus.

Fig. 2. Figure of CBOW by Mikolov et al. [8]

Fig. 3. Figure of Skip-grams by Mikolov et al. [8]

As the meaning of words are captured by the vectors, in another paper from the same year, Mikolov et al. [9] demonstrated how languages could be translated by mapping vector spaces between them. Using this method, they were able to achieve near 90% precision between English and Spanish.

While Word2Vec made a large leap in capturing meanings, these meanings are static. Word meanings change based on the context of surrounding words (e.g. “He is a **cool** guy” and “A fridge keeps food **cool**”), which cannot be represented using this method. Out-of-vocabulary (OOV) words can cause problems. If a word did not appear in the training data, it cannot be represented by Word2Vec. Additionally, if you wanted to use Word2Vec to represent a sequence of words or larger body of text, you would need to create your own means of doing so (e.g. averaging vector values of all words in the text). However, we cannot capture word order within the context (e.g. “The wolf ate the chicken” and “The chicken ate the wolf” will be represented in the same way).

2) **Doc2Vec**: Doc2Vec (or Paragraph Vector) [10] aimed to solve the issue of representing larger pieces of text while preserving the structure of the document. It extended Word2Vec to represent variable-length pieces of text (from paragraphs to full documents). When used for information retrieval, it was found that the error rate of Doc2Vec was 3.82%. This was a significant improvement compared to vector averaging of Word2Vec, which had an error rate of 10.25%.

3) **FastText**: To capture OOV words and morphology (prefixes and suffixes), it was proposed to extend Word2Vec to use n-gram token instead of words. In their paper “Bag of Tricks for Efficient Text Classification” [11], Joulin et al. found that their method known as “FastText” performed on par with other Deep Neural Network methods, while training much faster (taking minutes instead of hours) and using lesser hardware

(20-thread CPU vs NVIDIA Tesla K40 GPU).

C. Contextualised Embeddings

Unlike static embeddings (e.g. Word2Vec), contextualised embeddings produce different vectors based on the text surrounding a word (to use my previous example III-B1, “He is a **cool** guy” and “A fridge keeps food **cool**”) will produce different vectors for “**cool**”). While Transformers [12] are generally accepted as laying the foundation for modern pretrained language models, they were not directly proposed for vectorising text.

1) **Embeddings from Language Models**: In 2018, Peters et al. [13] proposed the use of “vectors derived from a bidirectional LSTM that is trained with a coupled language model” (LSTM - long short-term memory [14]). They entitled this method as ELMo (Embeddings from Language Models). ELMo creates embeddings for word tokens by looking at the complete sentence, both left-to-right and right-to-left (bidirectional). Previous methods of creating embeddings created a single vector per word, only capturing a single context. However, ELMo has the ability to capture context relative to the sentence in which the word token appears. This means that a word may have multiple vectors to better capture varied meanings.

The main limitation of LSTM [14] (and therefore ELMo) lies in its sequential nature: it processes tokens one at a time, which limits the degree of parallelization during training and inference. Furthermore, although bidirectional LSTMs can incorporate both past and future context, they may still struggle to fully capture long-range dependencies in text.

2) **Transformer-based models**: To overcome the limitations of LSTM-based architectures, Vaswani et al. [12] introduced the Transformer model (Figure 4), which relies entirely on self-attention mechanisms to process input sequences. Unlike RNNs (Recurrent Neural Networks) or LSTMs, Transformers do not process tokens sequentially; instead, they consider the entire sequence at once, allowing for greater parallelization and more effective modeling of long-range dependencies.

Transformer-based models have since become the backbone of modern pretrained language models. One of the earliest and most influential applications of this architecture to contextual embeddings is BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), introduced by Devlin et al. [15]. BERT is trained using a masked language modeling objective, where some tokens are hidden and the model learns to predict them using context from both the left and the right. This bidirectional training allows BERT to generate rich contextualised embeddings that are highly effective for a variety of NLP tasks.

While transformer-based embeddings are contextual and powerful, they are not without limitations. Issues such as sub-word tokenisation artifacts, poor alignment with task-specific goals, and lack of interpretable distance metrics can affect their effectiveness in certain applications. Additionally, the high dimensionality and context dependence of these vectors may

hinder performance in resource-constrained or unsupervised settings.

Fig. 4. The Transformer-model architecture by Vaswani et al. [12]

A comparison of all the techniques spoken about in this section can be seen in Table I.

D. Recent Trends

Since the introduction of Transformers and models such as BERT III-C2, the majority of research has revolved around Transformer-based methods. RoBERTa was released by Liu et al. [16] in 2019, where they claimed to have improved the training procedure of BERT [15], with improved performance on various benchmarks such as GLUE (General Language Understanding Evaluation). DistilBERT was developed by Sanh et al. in their 2020 paper entitled “DistilBERT, a distilled version of BERT: smaller, faster, cheaper and lighter” [17]. DistilBERT claimed to “reduce the size of a BERT model by up to 40%, while retaining 97% of its language understanding capabilities and being 60% faster”. To combat the quadratic complexity of BERT, Zaheer et al. introduced “BigBird” [18] in 2021. In their paper, they proposed that their sparse attention mechanism, using global, local, and random tokens, could reduce complexity from quadratic to linear.

However, recent research has also explored alternatives to the Transformer architecture, particularly focusing on addressing the computational limitations of attention mechanisms. One such approach is the Hyena operator, introduced by Poli et al. (2023) [19]. Hyena is a new technique designed to do a similar job to the “attention” mechanism in language models, but it’s more efficient for long sequences. Instead of using attention, Hyena mixes together long, indirect ways of looking at the data (like very long-range filters) with a

way to control what information is important at each step. This combination allows Hyena to process long texts without needing as much computation as attention, improving accuracy on tasks involving sequences of thousands to hundreds of thousands of tokens. Hyena demonstrates the potential to match Transformer quality in language modeling tasks.

IV. OBSERVATIONS AND RESEARCH GAPS

It is clear that the majority of research and development of recent years has been put towards optimising the size and complexity of Transformer based models. DistilBERT [17] reduced the size of the BERT model while maintaining most of its language understanding, and BigBird [18] improved BERT’s complexity with their sparse attention. Even in the case of Hyena [19], while not exactly a Transformer model, it is still based on the general concept, focusing on replacing the attention mechanism.

A comprehensive analysis of various attention-based models (e.g. BERT, BigBird) and attention alternatives (e.g. Hyena) for text classification with a focus on performance both for effectiveness and efficiency could provide valuable insights. Such a study could investigate the trade-offs between model size, computational cost, and classification accuracy across different datasets.

Furthermore, while much progress has been made in optimising Transformer models, there remains a need for research into novel vectorisation techniques that move beyond the attention mechanism. Exploring radically different approaches could potentially lead to breakthroughs in both performance and efficiency. For example, methods that better capture long-range dependencies in text with reduced computational overhead would be highly beneficial.

V. METHODOLOGY

For this review, I focused on using IEEE Xplore and Google Scholar. Occasionally, it was necessary to search for papers using a Google search (particularly the older papers such as “A STATISTICAL INTERPRETATION OF TERM SPECIFICITY AND ITS APPLICATION IN RETRIEVAL” [6]), as I was unable to access them on either database.

Keywords I used to find reviews include “Text Vectorisation” (or “Vectorization”), “Text Vectorisation Technique”, “Vectorisation”, “Survey”, “Review”, “Transformer”, “Embeddings”, “BERT”, “Hyena”, and combinations of each.

Occasionally, I would find my search results contained many papers regarding image vectorisation, leading me to exclude the word “Image”. When researching “Hyena”, it became important to include other terms (such as “text vectorisation”), as there was a large overlap with biological studies. While much of this review necessitated researching older papers (e.g. Distributional structure [4], Term-weighting approaches in automatic text retrieval [7], etc), where possible I tried to limit my search results to works from the last 5 years (i.e. 2020 - 2025).

VI. CONCLUSION

The landscape of text vectorisation has undergone transformative changes. From the humble beginnings of BoW, text vectorisation has evolved to capture word importance, meaning, and context. Each innovation has aimed to capture the intricacies of human language more effectively, addressing the limitations of previous methods, but not without cost. State of the art Transformer based methods are computationally expensive, demanding significant resources for training and inference. While there has been a clear focus on optimising Transformer-based models, more research needs to be done the efficacy and efficiency of the underlying attention mechanisms when compared to emerging competitors.

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